

CoARA Action Plan, November 2024

Tilburg University

TiU & CoARA: Responsible research assessment towards 2027

By signing the European [‘Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment’](#) (ARRA) TiU committed to prepare an action plan that translates the commitments in the Agreement into activities that contribute to a reform of its assessment of research, researchers and research groups. TiU’s CoARA action plan builds on existing initiatives and frameworks, showing TiU’s engagement with responsible research assessment and the efforts to constantly evaluate and improve the research assessment practices at our institution:

Programs	<i>R&R</i> National Recognition and Rewards program Recognition and Rewards program at TiU
	<i>SEP</i> Strategy Evaluation Protocol
	<i>IRAP</i> Institutional Research and Analytics Portal (IRAP)
Frameworks	<i>OS Framework</i> Tilburg University Open Science Framework
	<i>Team Science Vision</i> ‘Towards a Vision for Team Science at Tilburg University’
	<i>Impact Vision</i> Tilburg University Impact Vision

The Agreement endorses the objectives of the national Recognition & Rewards program and inspires the implementation and evaluation of the SEP, using responsible data-driven indicators for qualitative research evaluation. In line with TiU's core values curious, caring, connected and courageous, TiU's action plan emphasizes the importance of Open Science, Team Science and Impact in responsible research assessment.

Existing frameworks and initiatives

Figure 1. Responsible research assessment at TiU: Existing frameworks and initiatives

Recognition & Rewards

TiU is a signatory of the national Recognition & Rewards Program. In line with the nationwide R&R program's roadmap, '[Room for everyone's talent](#)', TiU set up its own R&R program and is currently implementing the program's five focal points to achieve the following:

1. Diversification of career paths;
2. Attention to the individual and to the team;
3. Focus on quality in criteria for recruitment, selection, development, and promotion;
4. Recognition for Open Science; and
5. Encouraging Connected Leading (internal program).¹

Open Science Framework

The R&R Program led to the development of the 'Tilburg University Open Science Framework' in 2023. It was drafted in collaboration between academic and professional staff, describing the future situation of Open Science at TiU. Focus points are Research Data and Infrastructure, Open Access, and Public Engagement.

TiU is currently implementing its OS Framework, as a joint effort between the Schools' Research Support Teams, Library & IT Support, and the Academic Services Policy Staff. It involves reforming research assessment on many levels, from how to assess the openness of an individual researcher's output to defining indicators for Open Science in the evaluation of research groups. The best practices learned from the OS Framework's implementation lead the way for TiU's Team Science Vision and TiU's Impact Vision to be translated into frameworks for implementation.

Team Science Vision

In 2023 (updated 2024), TiU published its policy brief 'Towards a Vision for Team Science at Tilburg University'. It describes TiU's perspective on the merits of Team Science, developing practical starting points for its implementation, charting national and international best practices for Team Science. TiU's TS Vision will be translated into a framework for implementation at our institution.

Impact Vision

Part of the TiU R&R program is the university-wide engagement with the theme of societal impact. The Impact Vision working group at TiU is creating an Impact Vision for the university, focusing on our impact-related ambitions. We want to reward researchers for non-traditional output, such as the

¹ <https://www.tilburguniversity.edu/about/organization/recognition-rewards>

publication of popular science books, research projects that involve Citizen Science, and making their datasets and software available in a FAIR manner.

SEP

The guiding principles of the national R&R position paper ‘Room for everyone’s talent’ were also incorporated in the national protocol that is used to evaluate the quality of research conducted at Dutch research institutes. Committees of Dutch and international experts and peers evaluate research units and institutes through review visits. The evaluation criteria and procedures are described in the Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP). The revised SEP ([SEP 2021-2027](#)) that was published in 2020, facilitates a broader system of recognition and rewards by basing the evaluation on the research units' own goals and strategy and focusing less on numerical data. Research units determine for themselves which indicators they consider relevant for evaluation of the unit's research. Evaluation committees will no longer assign scores in their report, instead they provide a critical substantive opinion and recommendations for the future.

In 2024, TiU implemented a new governance cycle surrounding the SEP, which research departments are currently using to facilitate a smooth (self-)assessment process. From 2024 to 2027, this reformed institutional research quality assurance cycle will be implemented and updated, incorporating internal and national evaluations of the SEP. TiU will keep taking into account new approaches to research and research output in proposing responsible research assessment practices. We focus on creating balanced indicators to evaluate the merit and quality of Open Science, societal impact, and Team Science in research practices.

IRAP: Data-driven monitoring

The Institutional Research and Analytics program (IRAP) supports the university to become a data-driven organization where business intelligence and analytics are part of daily operations. IRAP offers various reports via its portal, allowing users to access information on relevant topics. IRAP-reports are currently used as data-driven support for qualitative research assessment in research groups’ self-evaluations following the SEP.

In 2025, IRAP will create a new report focused on ‘research quality’: This dashboard allows us to collect and review information on research quality on a structural basis. Such a report enables an efficient, data-driven way of monitoring actions and output within the institutional research quality assurance cycle.

Commitments and actions

CoARA Commitment	Current situation (September 2024)	Objectives and actions 2024-2028
1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.	<p>The TiU Schools are working on new and revised HR policy, reflecting the vision and principles of R&R and CoARA.</p> <p>TiU's School of economics and management (TiSEM) is implementing their new HR policy (d.d. November 2023), which explicitly mentions following the vision and principles of R&R and CoARA.</p>	<p>All TiU Schools finalize and implement new and revised HR policy, reflecting the vision and principles of R&R and CoARA.</p>
	<p>The Impact Vision is being formulated. It focuses on recognizing and rewarding non-traditional research output and career paths.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Translating the Impact Vision into a framework for implementation. 2. Implementing the Impact Vision Framework.
	<p>TiU has applied for funding at NWO² to improve on the rewarding and recognition of Open Science activities of staff members via the OSNL call 'Recognising and Rewarding Open Science'</p>	<p>Execute the project 'Recognising and rewarding Open Science in policy and practice of academic work' in 2025.</p>
	<p>Research units have developed new indicators to monitor research performance in preparation for their next research evaluation</p>	<p>The indicators will be evaluated and updated towards the next increment of the research quality assurance cycle following the SEP (2027-2033).</p>

² The Dutch Research Council (NWO) is one of the most important science funding bodies in the Netherlands and realizes quality and innovation in science. Each year, NWO invests almost 1 billion euros in curiosity-driven research, research related to societal challenges and research infrastructure. See <https://www.nwo.nl/en> for more information.

	using the Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) 2021-2027.	
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators	The Schools have adjusted assessment criteria to align them with the Recognition and Rewards Program.	The annual consultation interviews (Performance & Talent Development Interviews) address the researcher's Open Science and Team Science practices, and their work's impact.
	The internal SEP guidelines, based on the SEP 2021-2027, are approved by the Executive Board. Five research units are writing self-assessment reports based on those guidelines, focusing on qualitative and narrative arguments, supported by case-studies and data-driven arguments.	All research units will write their self-assessments based on the TiU SEP guidelines.
	The responsible use of quantitative indicators is strengthened by the IRAP program and portal. The three research units that have written self-assessment reports use the portal and the generated reports as data-driven arguments in the self-assessments.	TiU will have a SEP factsheet ready in 2024, detailing the Dutch research university landscape for committee members reviewing a research unit. Increase the efficiency of institutional data delivery on research quality by achieving a structural solution (dashboard) in the IRAP portal, making data delivery less time-consuming and less error-prone.
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index	TiU research units are evaluated every six years according to the SEP. The most recent version of this protocol (SEP 2021-2027) states that the use of the Journal Impact Factor is not allowed. The use of individual bibliometric indicators such as the h-index is strongly discouraged. Following the TiU SEP guidelines, the research units do not use those metrics in their research assessments.	TiU will conduct a project focusing on evaluating the use of responsible (biblio-)metrics and sustainable rankings. Following the project outcomes, policy on this will be formulated for the coming years.
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment		

<p>5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to</p>	<p>TiU is implementing its R&R program and has a dedicated R&R program management team. The further implementation of responsible research assessment in TiU’s research quality assurance cycle is prioritized.</p>	<p>The R&R program is a structural initiative of TiU’s strategic plan 2024-2027, building on existing research assessment practices and their constant evaluation. Responsible research assessment and its evaluation is a focal point in TiU’s research quality assurance cycle.</p>
	<p>The TiU Academic Services Policy Staff Research has a dedicated policy advisor for ‘research quality’ (1 FTE) .</p>	<p>‘Research quality’ will stay a structural dossier for the Academic Services Policy Staff Research.</p>
<p>6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes</p>	<p>The IRAP program was highly successful and is now a structural part of TiU’s organization as the IRAP portal.</p>	<p>The IRAP portal will be expanded with dashboards and reports on ‘research quality’, aligning data-driven information gathering with responsible use of indicators.</p>
	<p>The implementation of the OS Framework and the creation of the Team Science and Impact Visions strengthen the development and review of responsible research assessment criteria, tools and processes.</p>	<p>The use of new criteria, tools and processes will be considered as well as the possible development of guidelines for metrics and indicators, based on the OS Framework and the Team Science and Impact Visions, in relation to the SEP.</p>
<p>7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use</p>	<p>The TiU SEP guidelines for self-assessments provide transparent communication on how to evaluate research based on responsible indicators and why we opt for reformed research assessment. The Research Support Teams in the Schools and the Academic Services Policy Staff Research both provide guidance during the internal review process of the self-assessments.</p>	<p>For the new SEP (2027-2033), TiU will again write its own SEP guidelines to assist research units with the evaluation of their research and the creation of their self-assessment reports.</p>
	<p>We share information on R&R, Open Science, Team Science, Impact, IRAP and CoARA on our intranet.</p>	<p>We will continue to share and update information on R&R, Open Science, Team Science, Impact, IRAP and CoARA on our intranet.</p>

<p>8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition</p>	<p>A Dutch National CoARA Chapter is being established. TiU has provided input for the nature and workings of the chapter.</p>	<p>As signatory of ARRA, TiU will be involved with the Dutch National CoARA Chapter.</p>
	<p>TiU staff involved in the R&R movement are actively involved in the national online R&R platform RRview, where Dutch research institutions exchange best practices on R&R.</p>	<p>TiU staff involved in the R&R movement remain actively involved in the national online R&R platform RRview.</p>
<p>9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the Commitments</p>		<p>The TiU CoARA Action Plan will be shared on Zenodo Progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the Commitments at TiU will be shared on the national online R&R platform RRview.</p>
<p>10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research</p>	<p>In June 2024, the results of the Culture Barometer Recognition & Rewards were released: A survey conducted among scientists in The Netherlands in early 2024.</p>	<p>Progress on R&R will be monitored both at a national and institute level by repeating the Culture Barometer survey in 2026.</p>